

DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE SOCIOLOGISTS BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. The article analyzes the integrative aspects of developing the social competence of future sociologists in accordance with modern requirements. Modern society demands that the future sociologist have scientific and innovative potential, be flexible and sensitive to rapidly developing social changes and conditions. In this regard, interdisciplinary integration develops in them social, communicative, personal qualities as well as professional skills.

Key words: integrative approach, social competence, future sociologist, communicative competence, professional potential, interdisciplinary integration, form, method, tool.

INTRODUCTION.

In the context of modernization of the social sphere, the development of social competence is of particular importance for the training of future sociologists. Without a sufficient level of social competence, a modern student (including future sociologists) will be unable to act effectively. In the didactics of professional-oriented social and humanitarian sciences education, the principles of professional-pedagogical training processes are regarded as the most important category, thereby enhancing the professional skills of future sociologists when working with various groups and strata of society. In this regard, the Decree No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019, "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030," issued by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, as well as the decree of February 22, 2019, "On Measures to Support the Conduct of Sociological Research by the State," confirm the relevance of work in this area and the necessity of continuously analyzing the attitudes of all segments of the population toward the prevailing socio-economic processes through the study and formation of public opinion.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. In our Republic, the integration of pedagogical and information technologies and the introduction of electronic and distance learning into the teaching process have been examined by U.Sh. Begimqulov [1], R.X. Djurayev [3], and N.I. Taylaqov [8]; the issues of developing students' professional competencies through an integrative approach

have been researched by E. Ismoilov [4], while the problems of forming foundational and subject-specific competencies in students have been investigated by, among others, B.Sh. Xasanova [7, p. 110].

B.Sh. Khasanova defined the system of forming competencies in students based on an integrative approach as consisting of the process of forming basic competencies in students based on the integration of pedagogical and information technologies using the effectiveness of educational content, teaching forms and methods. The stages of the integrative approach are as follows: interojection - the student accepts the knowledge he is acquiring based on his individual capabilities into his inner world with integrative motives [7, p. 65].

Based on the analysis of pedagogical and socio-psychological literature, we can conclude that the process of integration in education should be considered as a dialectically interconnected system of scientific ideas about certain or other phenomena, aspects and features of the material world or social life that constitute the subject of academic science, in order to develop comprehensive, integrated knowledge in students. Note that this approach does not violate the necessary existing differentiation of scientific disciplines. On the contrary, in the study of each individual subject, differentiation and integration act as two opposing and interrelated processes. Such dialectical harmony makes it possible to identify additional reserves for further improvement and rationalization of specialist training in an educational institution. Integration is a necessary attribute of the modern educational process. The purpose of didactics is to provide the teacher with effective tools for the purposeful integration of knowledge.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Analyzing the essence and content of the integrative approach and the foundations of its integration theory in the higher education system makes it possible to define the structure of the integrative approach in higher education and to identify the following levels: interdisciplinary, intra-disciplinary (inter-subject), interpersonal and intra-personal integrations. Therefore, from the perspective of an integrative approach, education is viewed as a process and result of pedagogical integration (interdisciplinary, intra-disciplinary, interpersonal and personal integration).

There is a difference between external and internal integration in education. External integration involves constructing a global educational space by consolidating the accumulated experience of various countries, as well as by integrating different types of activities—such as science, educational institutions, and production; various types of educational institutions; and different subjects or academic disciplines. Internal integration, on the other hand, is understood as the integration of components within a single type of activity, one subject, or within the framework of a single topic [6]. Internal integration is crucial for our research, as it

serves to create integrative systems for courses, disciplines, new and innovative technologies, and students - that is, for the organizational forms and methods of training and educating future sociologists.

“Integral education is understood as the assimilation of fundamental ideas and concepts that form the basis for incorporating knowledge through integration into the content of education and for shaping value relationships with the surrounding world” [5, 20-b.]. To develop the social competence of future sociologists, the use of an integrative approach will be effective if we achieve integrity, internal unity, and appropriate influence and interaction of all elements. The interaction of levels of integrative approaches in higher education is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The interaction of levels of integrated approaches in higher education

Let's take a closer look at the content of each level of integration as part of the professional training of future sociologists.

Interdisciplinary integration of general humanitarian and socio-economic sciences, general professional sciences, specialized sciences, and elective sciences at the university is carried out on the basis of integration ideas and system-forming concepts at the university: it covers education, its goals, the quality of education, the tasks and prospects of education, human development, the formation of professional consciousness, the content of education, methods of knowledge, modern educational technologies, in particular, active learning technologies, pedagogical creativity, professional skills, etc.

This type of integration directs higher education towards the implementation of a strategic goal - to form a professional worldview in students for orientation in the educational field and the successful solution of complex professional problems. Thanks to an integrated approach to educational content, future sociologists will

have the ability to demand and use the scientific content of all disciplines as a methodological, theoretical, and technological tool for solving interdisciplinary professional problems. Interdisciplinary integration continues and builds on intra-disciplinary integration.

Intra-subject integration (inter-topic) is based on understanding the subject as a differentiated and integrative system. Establishing semantic, meaningful, structural, and technological connections between sections and topics of a subject makes it possible to organize its study as a system open to new connections. Integration within the discipline is achieved through the modular construction of the curriculum content, which allows for the formation of system-forming connections and the integration of theory and practice. The result of integration within the discipline is expressed in the theoretical and methodological preparation of the future specialist (sociologist) for successful professional activity and is ensured by the integrity of the educational process.

In the educational process, implementing intra-disciplinary integration can be achieved through the resonant coordination of students' active engagement in knowledge and the developmental educational activities of teachers, based on collaboration, joint action, and a dialogic approach.

Also, during the research process, a technological model for developing social competence in future sociologists was developed based on an integrative approach (see Table 1).

Table 1

A technological model for developing social competence in future sociologists based on an integrative approach

№	Integrative sciences	Topics	Elements of social competence	Integrative form, methods and tools
1	Social psychology	Communication Social and interpersonal relationships Psychology of large and small groups	The ability to analyze social and interpersonal relationships in the research process. Adequate use of verbal and nonverbal communication tools. Emotional richness in speech, attractive forms of communication, unique voice, making and managing dialogues, use of language tools. Studying behavioral motives through analyzing the	Integrative work form: mass. Integrative methods: training, game, special techniques. Integrative tools: handouts and

		Ethnopsyc hology and religion	socio-psychological characteristics of different groups, strata, and peoples	special equipment
2	General sociology	The individual as a product of social relations. Sociological research methods	The formation of the "ME" doctrine in the individual, the formation of values and universal cultural competencies. Socialization, cultural norms, and social role- playing skills. Acquire skills in conducting independent sociological surveys and adhering to communication ethics	Integrative work form: discussion and debate. Integrative methods: social work methods, social survey analysis. Integrative tools: statistical and analytical materials Practical work at the sociological research center
		Social relations	Skills for correctly analyzing types of social relationships (collaboration, cooperation, conflict, alienation, discrimination). Skills for properly organizing consensus, stability, and cooperation to achieve the successful functioning of social systems	
3	Sociolo gy of family and gender	Family behavior: socialization , marriage, self- preservation , reproductive health. A sociological approach to	Can analyze the factors influencing the transformation of the family in modern society from the perspective of their impact on the socialization of the individual. Can research the socio- psychological aspects of gender socialization in the family based on a professional approach	Integrative work form: discussion and debate. Integrative methods: social work methods, social survey analysis. Integrative

		the study of interpersonal relationships in the family		tools: statistical and analytical materials
4	Digital and information technologies	Working with modern information technology educational tools Processing statistical data using spreadsheets Data analysis	Skills in working with sociological data through information technology, analyzing it, and preparing reports Skills in summarizing sociological research results and developing proposals using various diagrams and graphs Skills in statistical data analysis using SPSS software	Integrative form of work: individual and group Integrative methods: social work methods, social survey analysis. Integrative tools: statistical and analytical materials Practical work at a sociological research center

The investigated integrative approach and its corresponding educational models help address certain pressing tasks in modern higher education. Namely, they support the effective acquisition of social competencies by future sociologists; foster the development of practical research competencies that enable professional decision-making; encourage independent inquiry in research activities; enhance cognitive engagement; cultivate positive dialogue with values; and develop the creative ability that establishes didactic and social conditions to assist students (future sociologists) in fully and successfully adapting to sociological practice.

In higher education, interpersonal integration is regarded as a necessary direction for collaboration and co-creation, facilitated by the multifaceted openness of a dialogic space for mutual cooperation. Its role in the educational process is to

assist the social and personal development of the prospective specialist (sociologist) through self-learning, self-education, group research activities, scientific creativity, and the advancement of modern educational technologies. The outcome of such integration is manifested in the organizational and communicative preparedness for future professional activity.

Personal integration is based on the idea of an individual's integrative nature and on the principle of the wholeness of professional and personal development. This approach manifests itself through the absence of a direct cause-and-effect relationship between the externally expressed means of integration (operations, methods, actions) and the integrative outcome, while preserving the inner meaning of the observable substantive expressions and phenomena. As A. Danilyuk pointed out, "integration is a distinctive method of working with information and knowledge, both in general culture and specifically in education, which ensures the development of the learning consciousness" [2, p. 9]. Thus, for us, the outcome of personal integration appears as the assimilation of professional knowledge into consciousness.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it should be emphasized that sociological specialization in the teaching of sociology offers a key advantage of a science-based approach, both in accounting for the unique characteristics of presenting sociological knowledge and in providing opportunities to develop the social competencies of future sociologists across a wide range of disciplines. This approach enables us to design a curriculum that integrates the analysis of pressing issues in modern society, the modern individual, and contemporary science.

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